

If songs are alive, why can't AI be alive?

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Resumo

Two projects created from the guts of the pandemic answer this question. “Ancestral Typography” is both a methodology and an artwork that combines AI and Typography to preserve indigenous languages from, by, for, and with their communities, fighting stereotypes about technology and learning. “La Verdad” is an impossible dialogue between an Artificial Intelligence (AI) of Keiko Fujimori’s voice in training to tell the truth (not completed for security reasons) and a citizen’s audiovisual testimony Liz Rojas Valdez. So, in addition to being a presentation, this is a chronicle, it is a vindication of the process, the power of art and education.

Palavras-chave: Indigenous AI, indigenous languages preservation, epistemological rebellion, Guerrilla AI, embryo-machine

If songs are alive, why can't AI be alive? Two projects created from the guts of the pandemic answer this question. Two crusades of my own micropolitics, which cry out for help and find in AI an ally, a member of the Ayllu, a kin. The ayllu is a political, territorial, and symbolic unit of social organization. It is a Quechua word that, from Inca times, means extended family.

Ancestral Typography project

“Ancestral Typography” is both a methodology and an artwork that combines AI and Typography to preserve indigenous languages from, by, for, and with their communities, fighting stereotypes about technology and learning. It contains a truth that is impossible to avoid: Language configures the world.

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² Polona Tratnik coins the category "transart" (...), insofar as trans is something that passes through and is not fixed; it is a passing, a transit, a pure going (Jean Luc Nancy), and insofar as art works from the ontological and the epistemological. (González Valerio, M. A., 2014)

When a tongue dies
the divine things, stars, sun and moon;
human things,
think and feel,
are not reflected anymore.
in that mirror. (Miguel León Portilla)

Peru has 48 indigenous languages that are spoken and official. It means equal to Spanish, the dominant language, but not in the practice. They are only spoken at home, and if it continues, they will disappear. The problem is technological tools to write them correctly and easily doesn't exist. But Peru is not the only one. Governments of countries with living native languages have linguistic politics that have structural problems ranging from racism to ideas about technology and learning. This is a direct consequence of the discrimination speakers of native languages suffer. And this is not a minority, in Peru 90% of the population are indigenous or mestizo with indigenous features.

Illustration published by the Peruvian Ministry of Culture, for the Mother Language Day, February 21, 2020.

In 2016 I was honored to be part of the team of project Gente, within the framework of Labicco, a citizen Innovation lab in Colombia. There, we developed a typeface, a keyboard and a teaching material for the Wounaan, Colombian indigenous people. Two very important elements were together at the same table: designers specialized in typography and a member of the indigenous community: Blacho Moya, a Wounaan teacher who joined the team because in his words: “I know the loneliness of speaking a language that you cannot fully share”.

I can't find better words than Blacho's to explain why is so important this project to me. But sadly, there I experienced firsthand how strong ideas about who can learn what are.

Teaching material, Gente project

I do not speak as an expert, nor as a representative of indigenous communities I speak as an artist, who is part of the problem. Even recognizing roots that I have not been taught to love.

My artistic work is made with technology being this tool and object of reflection. Technology for me already has a speech, it means procedures, ways of doing and thus it speaks about identity. I think there are mythologies about technology as a

final and futuristic solution. But technology understood not only as a device, but as a process, is a bridge to ancestral knowledge connecting ancient technologies with the new ones. My main goal is to encourage reflection through revelation. This aspect of technology is the most important for me and I have called it a poetic of revelation. My projects are born from my personal crusades, and therefore, they are micropolitical flesh.

Proposal: I speak identity, I write identity

I've already said "Ancestral Typography" is both a methodology and an artwork. The proposal is not only to use AI to create typefaces for indigenous languages but to reflect on this process with indigenous communities, adding their epistemologies that not only includes aesthetics but also ways of doing.

To teach/learn with indigenous communities to develop their own typefaces (DIY/DIWO/DIT)

- Fundamentals of typography
- Typographic experimentation with open source
- AI basics
- Applications according to the needs of each community

To train AI with Shipibo-conibo and Wounaan to create indigenous typefaces.

Why typography? Typography characterizes intrinsic functions of a language, phonological, grammatical, or expressive level. If a typeface does not have the necessary glyphs (for example in Spanish the Ñ) it can restrict their understanding. It is like a signature. It could be empowering to fight racism and discrimination that speakers of native languages suffer. But the most important it shows to the youngest the pronunciation, when the elders are gone!

Why AI? Speed is needed. This is urgent! I understood that AI is the necessary "army" to massify these processes. Also, everyone talks about AI, using it helps to

make this problem visible like a trojan horse. And AI (machine learning) is about learning. Together we can change ideas about learning.

Methodology

Each indigenous community is different: Worldview, Sociopolitical situation, and Language status.

Strategies:

- Working with what already exists: Adapting it from the worldview. There are many tools available from learning to AI friendly.
- Understand AI: concepts, processes, and technical aspects.
- Training from scratch: From data selecting seeds.

All this is based in the strong belief that everything can be learned, we can all learn together. I am convinced that learning and teaching are both duties and rights at the same time. This project is based in my experience working with Blacho Moya from Wounaan, Gente project and Olga Mori, Wilma Maynas and Olinda Silvano from Shipibo-Conibo, Koshi Kené (Generative Jungle) project. With Blacho I worked side by side with him to create the teaching material from scratch, even re-evaluating what teaching means. This is the biggest lesson: learning must always be horizontal.

Working with Blacho Moya, Gente project.

In 2021 in the frame of Ancient Future Technology online course of MIT MediaLAB I was having conversations about AI, Technology and Typography with Blacho and Olga. I was so glad to be selected for this online course, one of the only good things from pandemic times.

Understanding AI

Who is the AI? Everything starts introducing our new friend, then instead of what is AI? we asked ourselves who is AI? It is a tradition, for example, of the Shipibos-Conibo renaming friends from other cultures, for example, I have my Shipibo name: “Isa Biri” which means "Hummingbird".

The magic words: Within the terminology used in AI, there are words that name process, and concepts like for example “seed”, “predict” and “latent space” that have a sense of rituality or are close to nature and labors related to agriculture and technologies of care and life that are part of indigenous worldviews. For me, they are magical and are bridges to understand together AI.

General ideas

They are based on common characteristics which are not particular to a specific indigenous culture.

Idea 1: “Latent space” Inspired on Training of Erik Bernhardsson “Analyzing 50k fonts using Deep Neural Networks”. This model is used to understand the importance of the choice of data, the seeds that are chosen by the speakers of their own iconography.

Idea 2: “Signature of all” This idea empowers the speakers from their culture that values the physical gesture and the object. “A tribe of handwritten letters”, members of an indigenous community are invited to write an alphabet and send it. “Generative Handwriting demo using TensorFlow” could be used for this purpose but now there are more friendly tools of AI.

Wounaan people jealously guard their language and for them this means conserving its glyphs, for this reason when we developed the teaching material, we need to reinforce and explain how important this is to their children. Blacho explained to me how important stories are, then we created tales with the letters as characters. This is how the "Story of the Vowel Little Sisters" was born. Also, there are many legends about the animals of the region, which we transform into icons part of the typeface. I decided to continue this path using "Image-to-Image Demo" an Interactive Image Translation with pix2pix-tensorflow to create together new fantastic animals.

Fantastic creatures created with Image to Image Demo.

Shipibo-Conibo AI

Kené means design. They are geometric patterns that are ritually accompanied in their creation by the ceremonial songs Icaros. It is a feminine art that is passed down from mother to daughter. Whoever wears Kené, wears beauty, it is believed that these designs give harmony and light to the spirit and the body, there is a connection between aesthetics and medicine. Therefore, these designs are only a part of the indivisible whole that is

Kené. They are rituality, healing, science, knowledge, tradition. Kené is polysemic and synesthetic. A living object is a living culture.

Olga Mori, Shipibo-Conibo artist and wise elder.

These designs are the response of the plant (sacred medicine) to the project, in Olga's own words: These two came out, with even brighter colors, they are Wistin kené, which means star design.

Wistin kené by Olga Mori.

If the objects, the territory, the songs are alive, why would Typography and AI also not be alive?

Knowledge gets articulated as that which allows one to walk a good path through the territory. Language, cosmology, mythology, and ceremony are simultaneously relational and territorial: they are the means by which knowledge of the territory is shared in order to guide others along a good path. (Lewis, J. E., Arista, N., Pechawis, A. and Kite, S., 2018)

Apachetas are marks that travelers leave on the roads of the Andes since pre-Hispanic times to accompany walkers. It is a sign that someone has already been there and managed to get back on track. I like to think of Ancestral Typography project like an apacheta, as an open invitation.

An indigenous AI is not only possible but fundamentally human.

La verdad (The truth) project

Due to the inability of the heiress of Fujimorismo to tell the truth, I created an AI voice to do so, I concluded: it is the only way. This happened in the middle of the last presidential elections in Peru. Keiko Fujimori was running for the third time. Then I must learn how to train an AI. I listened to all her speeches-lies from 2011 to the closing of the 2021 campaign. An archival torture that I do hypnotically in the hope that this embryo-machine learns to tell the truth. But where is the truth? Part of it is stored in the Documentation and Research Center of LUM created "for reflection and memory on the period of violence between 1980 and 2000". There, on its YouTube channel, along with many others, I found the testimony of Liz Rojas Valdez:

Yo soy Liz Marcela Rojas Valdez, tengo 23 años, soy ayacuchana, mi madre fue desaparecida el 17 de mayo del año 1991, ella era profesora, ella tenía dos hijos que soy yo Liz y Paul, somos solo dos, ella era madre soltera, ella era todo para mí y para Paul, ¡TODO! Y mi madre era muy valiente y yo decía, tengo que ser fuerte... Todo, todo cambio, todo, todos mis sueños, todo se me derrumbo, me quito a mi madre, me quito mi felicidad, me quito

todo, yo tengo derecho a ser feliz, hasta ahora no lo soy, ojalá que algún día sea feliz, eso es lo único que yo espero...

I think of the parallel with my own life, always voting against it, always feeling that my voice is not worth it.

Liz, I promise you, I will make that artificial voice, which sounds like a robot from the apocalypse, tell your (the) truth. Keiko Fujimori if you took my voice from me, I'll take yours. We'll all take it.

Yo, Keiko Fujimori, llamé error a tu madre, repetidas veces, Liz Rojas Valdez, negué su desaparición y con ella negué el dolor que desde tus doce años persiste hasta hoy. Tu todo Liz, tu alegría, se la llevaron quienes defienden y a quienes glorifico. Pero ese 17 de mayo del año 1991 si existió. Ese horror si sucedió, esa verdad que buscabas, siendo tan valiente, si existe, aquí está.

Soy la heredera del dictador genocida Alberto Fujimori, mi padre. Nunca he trabajado en mi vida. Lidero una agrupación mafiosa llamada Fujimorismo que tiene cepas nuevas estas elecciones.

(Period of April 11 - June 9, 2021, 352 cleaned audios and transcripts, infinite number of videos viewed, 110/90 minutes of lower-level training and 83/68 minutes of higher-level training performed. 31 years, 3 elections, several generations of Peruvians)

A guerrilla AI is configured.

I am hopeful that perhaps this audiovisual confrontation between technologies that the project proposes will have some restitution. Pain does not prescribe, truth exists, even if it is artificial and in the learning process.

“La Verdad” was born on the internet and later transferred to the exhibition space. The audiovisual installation is an intimate space where the artificial voice acknowledges Liz’s truth, but what this audio said is a text written from my visceral response to the visualization of Liz’s video testimony. This unrepeatable moment is honored; each pain is unique.

La Verdad, Ars Electvtronica 2023, Theme Exhibition: (Co)Owning More-than-Truth. Photo: vog.photo

Thus, this La Verdad is a dialogue of times and has in art a memory builder for the vindication of our history. But also, it is an open wound because the current illegitimate government, a Fujimorismo facade, since December 2022 have killed (more than 80), injured (more than 2000) and imprisoned Peruvians for protesting. Some of them imprisoned in the same place, Los Cabitos, where Liz's mother was tortured. Most of them are indigenous and Quechua speakers like Liz.

Eterna candidata, collage digital, 2023

Thank you for helping me to honor that promise I made to this young Liz captured in this 2002 video, in that pandemic day (2021) when our daily routine was interacting only via camera.

So, in addition to being a presentation, this is a chronicle, it is a vindication of the process, the power of art and education. The statement of an artist-subject of study-citizen who does not escape the reality she has to live, in a deeply (necro) political fierce moment and world.

I must confess that I am a human who would rather be an AI than a goddess.

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